

Soil apparent electrical conductivity sensor data for estimation of CI-based soil compaction status

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Abstract

Regionalization of soil properties is very important for successful site-specific field management. Soil compaction is a critical issue to be detected and managed due to its effects on crop growth. Soil compaction has been conventionally quantified as cone index (CI) measured by an ASABE-standard cone penetrometer, but this approach has limited capability of obtaining the spatially-dense data required for precision agriculture. A significant amount of past research has related CI with apparent soil electrical conductivity (ECa), and recently the potential of ECa to estimate subsoil compaction status through the stress-at-rest-coefficient (K₀), defined as the ratio of normal compaction and pre-compaction, was introduced. The objective of this study was to explore the potential of relating K₀ with ECa using data obtained from sites with wide ranges of soil texture, bulk density, and water content, properties that significantly affect both CI and ECa. The following data was collected from 35 sites in Missouri and Illinois fields: CI profile up to 75 cm with a 5-cm interval, ECa measured by EM38 and Veris devices, and depth-dependent soil properties such as soil texture, bulk density, and water content. First, K₀ values were calculated from CI profiles by depth and related to ECa measurements. Then, effects of the soil properties on the relationships between K₀ and ECa were investigated. Results of this study will provide insights on the effects of soil properties on soil compaction, and on the potential to use ECa to estimate the status of soil compaction.

Background

Information on variability and regionalization of soil properties is important for crop production using site-specific crop and field management (SSCM). In many cases, soils are sampled and analyzed through a series of laboratory tests. Even though laboratory tests provide accurate estimations of soil properties, this approach has problems related to the testing procedures (e.g., standardization, quality control) and/or sampling procedures (e.g., number of samples, sample preparation). Sensor-based estimation of soil conditions in real time (i.e., giving immediate readings) and in-situ may solve these issues. By obtaining much more data, a real-time soil sensor can tolerate much higher analysis errors while providing greater overall accuracy in SSCM applications (Sudduth et al., 1997).

Variables that have been most actively measured and used in SSCM are soil strength and apparent electrical conductivity. Soil strength is the ability or capacity of a particular soil in a particular condition to resist or endure an applied force (Guerif, 1994). Soil strength has been used to estimate the state of soil compaction since soil strength is strongly associated with compactness, packing density, relative bulk density, and drainable porosity (Canarache, 1991). In-field soil strength has traditionally been determined using a cone penetrometer (ASABE, 2013). The index of soil strength measured by a cone penetrometer, cone index (CI), is defined as the force per unit base area required to push the penetrometer through a specified small increment of soil. The cone penetrometer can characterize soil strength with depth and thereby provide information related to soil morphological characteristics (e.g., Mulqueen et al., 1977).

Sensing of apparent soil electrical conductivity (ECa) has been used extensively in SSCM. ECa is a measure of the ability of a material to transmit an electrical current and has been extensively used to estimate soil salinity. In non-saline soils, the usefulness of soil ECa stems from the fact that sands have a low conductivity, silts have a medium conductivity and clays have a high conductivity (Lund et al., 1999). Soil ECa has been shown to have associations with important soil chemical and physical

properties such as soil salinity, clay content and cation exchange capacity (CEC), clay mineralogy, soil pore size and distribution, soil water content, and temperature (Fritz et al., 1999; Sudduth et al., 2001; Sudduth et al., 2003). Since soil ECa is a composite measure of soil status and is affected by a number of soil properties, the conductivity measurements can be used in a variety of applications: for estimation of a specific soil property (Johnson et al., 2001), as an indication of crop productivity, or for delineation of management zones (Fraisse et al., 2001).

A significant amount of past research has investigated the relationship of CI to apparent soil electrical conductivity (ECa). Recently the potential of ECa to estimate subsoil compaction status through the stress-at-rest-coefficient (K_0), defined as the ratio of normal compaction and pre-compaction, was introduced. The objective of this study was to explore the relationship of K_0 to ECa using data obtained from sites with wide ranges of soil texture, bulk density, and water content, soil properties that significantly affect both CI and ECa.

Materials and methods

Study fields

Data were collected on fields in Missouri and Illinois. The Missouri field (F1, 35 ha) was located near Centralia, in central Missouri (39.230 N, 92.117 W). The Illinois field (WS, 16 ha) was near Bellflower, in east-central Illinois (40.301 N, 88.544 W). Both fields were managed in a minimum-tillage corn-soybean rotation for several years prior to data collection. The soils found at the Missouri site include the claypan soils of the Mexico series (fine, smectitic, mesic aeric Vertic Epiaqualfs) and the Adco series (fine, smectitic, mesic aeric Vertic Albaqualfs). These soils were formed in moderately-fine textured loess over a fine textured pedisegment and are classified as somewhat poorly drained. Surface textures range from silt loam to silty clay loam. The subsoil claypan horizon(s) are silty clay loam, silty clay or clay, and commonly contain as much as 50 to 60% smectitic clay. Topsoil depth above the claypan (depth to the first B horizon) ranged from less than 10 cm to greater than 100 cm.

Soils of the Illinois site include the Varna series (fine, illitic, mesic Oxyaquic Argiudolls), Drummer series (fine silty, mixed, superactive, mesic Typic Endoaquolls), and Chenoa series (fine, illitic, mesic Aquic Argiudolls). Surface textures include silt loam and silty clay loam. Drainage classes represented at the Illinois field range from poorly-drained to well-drained (Kravchenko et al., 2001).

Data collection

The following data were collected from 35 sites in the Missouri and Illinois fields: CI profile up to 75 cm with a 5-cm interval, ECa measured by EM38 and Veris devices, and depth-dependent soil properties including soil texture, bulk density, and water content. CI data were collected with the Veris Profiler 3000 (Veris Technologies, Salina, KS), a penetrometer that differed somewhat from ASABE Standard S313.2. Sudduth et al. (2004) described these differences and evaluated the operating characteristics of the Profiler 3000 in comparison to the standard. Within each field, 19 (F1) or 16 (WS) sampling sites were chosen by a soil scientist familiar with the soils in the particular field to include all the landscape positions and soil map units present. Penetrometer data were collected at the sampling sites in the spring of 2000 after soybean planting (24 and 25 May 2000 for F1 and 8 June 2000 for WS). Fifteen CI datasets were obtained at each site, with three replications spaced approximately 0.5 m apart along the row and five row positions spaced approximately 19 cm apart within each replication. For the drilled soybeans at F1, the five row positions were obtained from north to south coincident with the seed rows of the grain drill. For the planted (76 cm row spacing) soybeans at WS, the five row positions were trafficked row middle, trafficked shoulder, plant row, untrafficked shoulder, and untrafficked row middle. Gravimetric soil water content data was obtained at each site, on 15 cm depth increments, at the time of penetrometer data collection.

To obtain soil property information, one 4.0 cm diameter core 120 cm in length was obtained at each site using a hydraulic soil coring machine. Cores were examined within the field by a skilled soil scientist and pedogenic horizons identified. Samples for each horizon were analyzed at the University of Missouri Soil Characterization Laboratory using methods described by the National Soil Survey Center Staff (1996). Data were obtained for the following properties: sand, silt, and clay fractions (pipette method); CEC (ammonium acetate method); organic C; and total C. Bulk density was determined by horizon for the Missouri sites only.

The various types of profile data were obtained differently (i.e., by horizon or at fixed depths), so it was necessary to transform all datasets to a common depth increment for statistical analysis. A nominal 5 cm (2 in. actual) depth increment was chosen for this purpose. At each site, all 15 penetrometer readings were averaged to a single mean CI dataset. This CI data was then merged with the soil profile characteristic data on the 5 cm depth increments. Dense spatial datasets were available on these fields for comparison with and interpretation of penetrometer data. Soil electrical conductivity (EC) data were obtained on study fields in the fall of 1999 after corn harvest, using the Geonics EM38 and Veris 3100 ECa sensors (Sudduth et al., 2003). Elevation data were obtained by conventional surveying methods or real-time kinematic (RTK) GPS methods.

Analytical procedures

First, K_0 values were calculated from CI profiles by depth and related to ECa measurements. The K_0 concept was introduced by Hoefler et al. (2010), assuming that the horizontal stress component characterized the compaction state of the soil. They assigned penetration resistance (PR, equivalent to CI) values to the principal stress as a function of depth, normalized by CI at the greatest accessible depth. K_0 is the ratio of non-compacted state “a” and compacted state “b” in the zone of maximum compaction, often referred to as the “compaction pan” (Figure 1). Then, effects of the soil properties on the relationships between K_0 and ECa were investigated. Soil properties used in the study were soil bulk density, water content, and texture fractions (clay, silt, and sand).

Figure 1. Scheme for parameterizing K_0 over a depth of 0.3–0.4 m from the CI profile (from Hoefler et al., 2010)

Results and discussion

Relationships between K_0 and ECa were obtained, where ECa values were obtained by EM38, Vsh (Veris shallow reading), and Vdp (Veris deep reading) (Figure 2). The relationships for the two fields were similar for EM38 data, with slopes close to -1. For Veris data, the relationships were very poor for the Illinois field, but of similar accuracy to the EM38 relationship for the Missouri field. Regression slopes in the Illinois field were less than that in Missouri field for Veris and EM38 data. Relationships between K_0 and ECa may have been affected by shape of the CI profiles from the two fields. In general, on the Missouri field, the “compaction pan” CI values (first peaks) were greater than the deep-profile CI values, while that was often not the case for the Illinois field. Also the compaction pan CI values were clearer for the Missouri field, while there were sometimes multiple peaks and a less clear definition of the pan for the Illinois field.

Figure 2. Relationships between K0 and ECa, where ECa values were obtained by EM38 (left), Vsh (right), respectively

Effects of soil properties

Soil bulk density, water content, and texture fractions are factors affecting both CI and ECa. Relationships between K0 and soil properties at the deepest depth, at the depth of the first peak CI, and averaged over all depths were investigated. The relationships were different for the two fields, and also for soil properties at different depths (Figure 4). Bulk density might be thought of as related to the “a” parameter in the K0 calculation, and the relationship was better when the depth-averaged bulk density was used. For soil water content and total silt fraction, the relationships were better when the values at the depth of the first peak CI were used. The soil properties at the depth of the first CI peak might be related to ECa values, especially Veris shallow readings.

Relationships between K0 and EM38 were better when subset data were used. For example, the relationships were better for low ECa measured by EM38 (20~31) for the Missouri field and for high ECa measured by EM38 (31~40) for the Illinois field (Figure 5). These differences may have been due to differences in soil properties between the two fields. Silt contents were generally greater in the Missouri field, while soil water and clay contents were greater in the Illinois field.

Figure 4. Relationships of K0 and depth-averaged bulk density (left), water content at the depth of peak CI (right), respectively

Figure 5. Relationships between K0 and subsets of EM38-measured ECa: low ECa (20~31) for the Missouri field (left) and high ECa (31~40) for the Illinois field (right).

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